

Engineering Electrical Conductivity and Electronic Structure in Lithium Niobate via Targeted Doping

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Abstract

Lithium niobate (LiNbO₃, LN) is a versatile ferroelectric material widely used in acoustic and optoelectronic applications. This study examines the impact of magnesium (Mg) doping on the density of electronic states (DOS) and electrical conductivity of LN. By combining density functional theory (DFT) simulations with ferroelectric phase transition theory, we have modelled the evolution of the band gap (E_g) as a function of dopant concentration. Our results show that low Mg doping (up to 3.4%) considerably improves electrical conductivity by reducing both the energy of the band gap and Nb_L-type vacancy defects. Above this critical threshold, conductivity gradually decreases as a result of increased E_g and the formation of additional structural defects. These results provide valuable indications for the optimisation of LN-based inter-digital transducers (IDTs) and the design of high-performance acoustic devices.

Keywords: keyword Lithium Niobate; Electrical Conductivity; band structure; Surface Acoustic Wave De-vices.

1.Introduction

Lithium niobate (LiNbO₃ or LN) is a crystalline compound that has established itself as a key material in the field of functional materials, thanks to its exceptional piezoelectric, optical, and electrical characteristics [1,2]. These properties have made it indispensable in a range of technological applications, including nonlinear optics [3], optical communications, single-crystal nanodevices [4], acousto-optic systems [5], sensors, and piezoelectric components.

To fully harness the potential of LiNbO₃, it is essential to understand how variations in chemical composition can impact its intrinsic properties [6]. In particular, the nature and behavior of defects within the crystal lattice play a crucial role in its overall performance, as shown in various studies [7,9]. LiNbO₃ is commonly synthesized using the Czochralski (CZ) method [10], while vapor transport equilibration (VTE) is often applied to produce crystals with near-stoichiometric compositions [11]. At room temperature, the solid solubility range of LiNbO₃ lies between approximately 46% and 50.4% molar Li₂O. This range widens at higher temperatures, extending from 45% to 50% molar Li₂O at 1210°C [12].

In recent years, growing attention has been directed toward doping lithium niobate with selected elements to tailor its properties for specialized uses. Among the various dopants investigated, magnesium (Mg) stands out for its notable influence on both the crystal structure and electrical behavior of LN [13,19]. Titanium (Ti) is another important dopant, especially valued for its impact on the optical and electro-optical characteristics of LiNbO₃, making it highly relevant in waveguide fabrication [20]. Some studies suggest that the change in ordinary refractive index with increasing Ti concentration could be linked to a displacement of Ti ions within the xy-plane, although this hypothesis has yet to be definitively confirmed [21].

The main objective of this work is to develop a deeper understanding of how doping affects the structural and electronic properties of LiNbO₃—a material of critical importance for advanced optical and acoustic technologies. Specifically, the study focuses on the role of divalent Mg dopants in altering the crystal lattice, modifying the electronic density of states (DOS), and influencing electrical conductivity.

By employing density functional theory (DFT) simulations [22], along with models addressing ferroelectric phase transitions and structural defects in both pure and doped LiNbO₃, this research aims to:

- Analyze how Mg doping at various concentrations modifies the bandgap energy (E_g) and how these changes correlate with variations in electrical conductivity.
- Examine the impact of structural defects—such as vacancies and point defects—on the electronic structure and performance of the material.

Ultimately, the findings are intended to provide valuable guidance for optimizing lithium niobate by fine-tuning dopant type and concentration. These insights are particularly relevant for improving device performance in systems such as surface acoustic wave (SAW) resonators and nonlinear optical components, where precise control over structural and electronic properties is essential.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plan vibration and soft modes

In the work of Safaryan [23], the ferroelectric transition in lithium niobate (LiNbO₃) is attributed to a complex interplay between ion dynamics and thermal expansion of the crystal lattice, ultimately leading to a rearrangement of ion positions. His model successfully captures the essential ferroelectric properties of LiNbO₃ and its phase transition behavior.

To make the analysis feasible, Safaryan simplifies the problem by reducing the complex dynamics of the charged planes to a one-dimensional linear model of lattice vibration, taking into account only the electrostatic interactions between the nearest ions. This simplification plays an essential role in explaining the ferroelectric transition within its framework.

In the present study, we propose an extended version of this model by incorporating electrostatic interactions between nearest and second-nearest neighbors. This enhancement aims to provide a more complete and accurate description of the ferroelectric transition, particularly in non-stoichiometric and doped LiNbO₃ systems.

In the LN crystal structure, the planes are composed of Li⁺, Nb⁵⁺ and O²⁻ ions, which interact via long-range electrostatic forces. The equations of motion take into account the restoring forces resulting from these interactions. When second-neighbor interactions are included, additional terms must be introduced to reflect the extent of influence beyond adjacent planes.

Here, we define "a" as the lattice period, i.e. the distance between two successive oxygen planes.

Figure 1 illustrates the spatial arrangement of these ions in the unit cell at order s , as well as their respective displacements: u_s (Li⁺) for Li⁺, v_s (Nb⁵⁺) for Nb⁵⁺ and ξ_s (O²⁻) for O²⁻.

Figure. 1: Line, which shows the position of Li⁺, Nb⁵⁺ and O²⁻ ions in a linear lattice, with their corresponding displacements u_s , v_s and ξ_s along the c axis.

Considering the nearest-neighbor (interactions between ions in adjacent planes) and second-neighbor (ions separated by two planes) interactions, the equations of motion for the ions Li⁺, Nb⁵⁺, and O²⁻ can be written as follows:

$$M_1 \ddot{U}_s = C_{10}(\xi_s - \mu_s) + C_{21}(V_{s+1} - \mu_s) + C'_{10}(\xi_{s+1} - \mu_s) + C'_{21}(V_{s+2} - \mu_s)$$

$$M_2 \ddot{v}_s = C_{21}(\mu_s - v_s) + C_{20}(\xi_s - v_s) + C'_{21}(\mu_{s+1} - v_s) + C'_{20}(\xi_{s+1} - v_s) \quad (1)$$

$$M_0 \ddot{\xi}_s = C_{20}(V_s - \xi_s) + C_{10}(\mu_{s-1} - \xi_s) + C'_{20}(V_{s-1} - \xi_s) + C'_{10}(\mu_{s-2} - \xi_s)$$

Here, the terms C'_{10} , C'_{20} and C'_{21} account for the contributions from second neighbors, meaning ions located two planes apart along the trigonal c -axis.

The masses M_1 , M_2 and M_0 represent the respective masses of the Li^+ , Nb^{5+} , and O^{2-} ions. The interactions between the ions in adjacent planes are characterized by the elastic constants C_{ij} .

The choice of solutions in the form of plane waves, $u_s = ue^{i\omega t} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}_s}$ with $U_s = V_s$, μ_s ou ξ_s

And \mathbf{k} its wave vector, which we choose equals 0.

The coefficients C_{ij} for the LiNbO_3 crystal are determined using enhanced elastic constants based on Coulomb's law:

$$C_{ij} = -\frac{e^2 q_i q_j}{b(R_{ij}^0)^2} n. \quad (2)$$

where R_{ij} and R'_{ij} represent the distances between the nearest and second-nearest neighbors, respectively.

The specific interaction coefficients are:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{Li-O}} = C_{2-0} &= 3 \frac{e^2 q_i q_j}{b(R_{20}^0)^2} n; & C'_{2-0} &= 3 \frac{e^2 q_i q_j}{b(R'_{20}^0)^2} n \\ C_{\text{B-O}} = C_{1-0} &= 3 \frac{e^2 q_i q_j}{b(R_{10}^0)^2} n; & C'_{1-0} &= 3 \frac{e^2 q_i q_j}{b(R'_{10}^0)^2} n \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{\text{B-Li}} = C_{1-2} = -\frac{e^2 q_i q_j}{b(R_{12}^0)^2} n; \quad C'_{1-2} = -\frac{e^2 q_i q_j}{b(R'_{12}^0)^2} n$$

Here, q_0 , q_1 , and q_2 are the charges of the ions O^{2-} , Nb^{5+} , and Li^+ respectively, and b is the lattice constant. The parameters R_{ij} and R'_{ij} indicate the distances between the nearest and second-nearest neighbors.

After calculating the determinant ($\Delta=0$), we arrive at the following equation:

$$\omega^6 + A\omega^4 + B\omega^2 + D = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the coefficients A , B , and D depend on the interaction constants and the masses of the ions.

Were

$$A = -\frac{1}{m_2}(c_{12} + c_{20} + c'_{12} + c'_{20}) - \frac{1}{m_1}(c_{10} + c_{12} + c'_{10}) - \frac{1}{m_0}(c_{10} + c_{20})$$

$$\begin{aligned} B = & \frac{1}{m_1 m_2} (c_{12}^2 + c_{10} c_{20} + c_{12} c_{20} + c_{20} c'_{10} + c_{12} c'_{12} + c_{10} c'_{20} + c_{12} c'_{20} + c'_{10} c'_{20}) + \frac{1}{m_0 m_2} (c_{10} c_{12} + \\ & c_{10} c_{20} + c_{12} c_{20} + c_{10} c'_{12} + c_{12} c'_{20} + c_{10} c'_{20} - c_{20} c'_{20} - c'_{20}^2) + \frac{1}{m_1 m_0} (c_{10} c_{12} + c_{10} c_{20} + c_{12} c_{20} - c_{10} c'_{10} + \\ & c_{20} c'_{10} - c'_{10}^2) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D = & -\frac{1}{m_0 m_1 m_2} (c_{10}^2 (c_{20} - c_{12} - c'_{12} + c_{20}) - c'_{10}^2 (c_{12} + c'_{12} + c_{20}^2 + c'_{12} c'_{20} - c_{12} c'_{20}) + c_{10} (c_{12}^2 + \\ & 2c_{12} c_{20} - 2c_{12} c'_{10} + c_{20} c'_{10} + c_{12} c'_{12} + c_{20} c'_{12} + 2c_{12} c'_{20} - c_{20} c'_{20} - c'_{12} c'_{20} - c'_{20}^2) + c_{20} (c_{12}^2 + 2c_{12} c'_{12} - \\ & c_{12} c'_{10}) - c_{12} c'_{20}^2) \end{aligned}$$

There are several methods for solving the characteristic equation (4). A classic approach is the Cardan method.

we pose $\omega = z - \frac{B}{3}$ from which equation 3 becomes

$$z^3 + p\omega + q = 0$$

(6)

$$\text{where } p = \frac{3C-B^2}{3} \text{ and } q = \frac{2B^3-9BC+27D}{27}$$

we found that $\Delta = \left(\frac{q}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^3 = -5.31 \times 10^{170} < 0$, there are three distinct real roots, which corresponds to the fact that the system has three modes of vibration: an acoustic mode (the highest frequency) and two optical mod

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1^2 &= 2\sqrt{\frac{-p}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{3}\right) - \frac{B}{3} \\ \omega_2^2 &= 2\sqrt{\frac{-p}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta+2\pi}{3}\right) - \frac{B}{3} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\omega_3^2 = 2\sqrt{\frac{-p}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta + 4\pi}{3}\right) - \frac{B}{3}$$

Where $r = \sqrt{\frac{-p^3}{27}}$ and $\theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{-q}{2r}\right)$

After solving the system, we found the following values: $\omega_3^2 = 4.11 \times 10^{27}$, $\omega_2^2 = 2.56 \times 10^{28}$ et $\omega_1^2 = 1.20 \times 10^{29}$. The real solution corresponding to the soft mode of vibrations (acoustic mode) in stoichiometric LiBO_3 solid solutions is ω_1^2 .

In the case of non-stoichiometric lithium niobate, the frequency of the soft mode can be written analogously as:

$$\omega_{*1}^2 = 2\sqrt{\frac{-p^*}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta^*}{3}\right) - \frac{B^*}{3} \quad (8)$$

The frequencies ω_1^2 and ω_{*1}^2 are proportional to the phase transition temperatures, which is approximately 1200 °C for the stoichiometric material. Therefore, the expression for the transition temperature of non-stoichiometric ceramics can be derived as:

$$T_C^* = \frac{2\sqrt{\frac{-p^*}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta^*}{3}\right) - \frac{B^*}{3}}{2\sqrt{\frac{-p}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{3}\right) - \frac{B}{3}} T_C \quad (9)$$

The aforementioned relation enables the calculation of Curie temperatures for various vacancy models utilized in this study.

The expression of the quantities X and X* depends on the composition of the LN (stoichiometric or non-stoichiometric compositions) and the chosen lacunar model.

2.2 Estimating electrical conductivity

To investigate the electrical properties, in particular the electrical conductivity (σ), of pure lithium niobate (LiNbO_3 : LN) and magnesium-doped lithium niobate (LiNbO_3 : Mg), we applied the ferroelectric phase transition theory developed in this work. In addition, we evaluated defect models suitable for pure and doped lithium niobate. To this end, we used several samples of undoped lithium niobate that had previously been studied experimentally by A. Weidenfelder et al. These samples (1, 2 and 3) have respective molar ratios of $r_1 = [\text{Li}]/[\text{Nb}] = 0.947$, $r_2 = 0.98$ and $r_3 = 1$ [24].

In addition, we analyzed samples of magnesium-doped lithium niobate (LiNbO_3 : Mg), which had also been characterized experimentally by Nadège Meyer et al [25].

Electrical conductivity depends on temperature and follows Arrhenius' law ($\sigma(T) = \sigma_0 e^{-\frac{E_a}{K_B T}}$) [26]. The transition from stoichiometry to doping modifies the expression for conductivity by replacing T by T*, where T represents the temperature for a perfectly stoichiometric material, and T* applies to all other cases: non-stoichiometric, undoped and doped materials (since doping always modifies stoichiometry). In this context, to determine the relationship between the electrical conductivity of stoichiometric and non-stoichiometric or doped lithium niobate, we used the following ratio:

$$\frac{\sigma^*(T^*)}{\sigma(T)} = e^{-\frac{E_a}{K_B T^*}} e^{\frac{E_a}{K_B T}}$$

$$\sigma^*(T^*) = \sigma_0 e^{-\frac{E_a}{K_B T^*}} \quad (10)$$

Here, $\sigma^*(T^*)$ is the electrical conductivity of non-stoichiometric or doped LN at temperature T*, $\sigma(T)$ is the electrical conductivity of stoichiometric LN at temperature T, σ_0 is the pre-exponential factor, a characteristic constant specific to each LN sample, E_a is the activation energy, i.e. the energy required for an electron to move from one band to another or overcome an energy barrier, K_B is Boltzmann's constant ($K_B = 8.617 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV/K}$).

We determined the quantities X* (M_1^* , M_2^* ...) using the lacunar models mentioned in Table 1, and subsequently, the expression for T* becomes $T^* = f(x, y)T$

Therefore,

$$\sigma^*(T) = \sigma_0 e^{-\frac{E_a}{K_B f(x,y)T}}$$

(11)

Where x and y represent the non-stoichiometric composition and impurity concentration (in moles), respectively. This leads to the following equation:

$$\log(\sigma^*) = \log \sigma - \frac{E_a}{K_B f(x,y)T} \quad (12)$$

We can further simplify by defining $\alpha = \log \sigma^*$, $A = \log \sigma$, $B = -\frac{E_a}{K_B f(x,y)1000}$ et

$$\mu = \frac{1000}{T}, \text{ resulting in: } \alpha = A + B\mu$$

The charge and mass values of the LiNbO_3 compound doped with magnesium and tetravalent impurities are presented below:

$$q_{(\text{Nb})} = q_1 = 5; q_{(\text{Li})} = q_2 = 1; q_{(\text{O})} = q_0 = 2; q_{(\text{Mg})} = 2; M_{\text{Nb}} = M_1 = 92.9 \text{ a.u}; M_{\text{Li}} = M_2 = 6.94; M_{\text{O}} = M_0 = 16$$

The distances between the planes of ions in LiNbO_3 are as follows: $R_{\text{Nb-O}} (R_{10} = 0.883\text{\AA})$, $R_{\text{Li-O}} (R_{20} = 0.68\text{\AA})$ and $R_{\text{Li-Nb}} (R_{12} = 0.747\text{\AA})$ [27]

Figure 2. (a) Conventional hexagonal structure of pure lithium niobate (LiNbO_3) and (b) lithium niobate doped with MgO .

To evaluate the evolution of electrical conductivity as a function of impurity concentration and non-stoichiometric composition at constant temperature, the following relationship was used:

$$\log(\sigma^*) = \log \sigma - \frac{E_a}{K_B f(x,y)T} \quad (13)$$

The function $f(x,y)$ is determined on the basis of the vacancy models presented in Table 1. This function plays a crucial role in characterizing the electrical conductivity of lithium niobate (LN) as a function of non-stoichiometric composition (x) and dopant concentration (y).

The general formulation of $f(x,y)$ is given by

$$f(x,y) = \frac{2\sqrt{\frac{-p^*}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta^*}{3}\right) - \frac{B^*}{3}}{2\sqrt{\frac{-p}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{3}\right) - \frac{B}{3}} \quad (14)$$

Lithium niobate (LiNbO_3) is a material with intrinsic and extrinsic vacancy defects, such as lithium deficiency. This deficiency can lead to the occupation of lithium sites by niobium

ions, accompanied by vacancies (designated par□) and various defects on lithium and niobium sites. To represent these defects, several vacancy models have been proposed.

Case of Pure Lithium Niobate

For pure lithium niobate, we use the following vacancy model:

- For magnesium-doped lithium niobate with Mg concentrations (LNMg) below 3.4%:

- For magnesium-doped lithium niobate with Mg concentrations above 3.4%:

The mixed vacancy model takes into account vacancies at both lithium and niobium sites. In these models, the negative sign associated with vacant niobium sites ($\square_{Nb\ -\frac{1}{20}x}$) in the pure model and ($\square_{Nb\ -(x+0,64y)}$) in the doped model indicates a relative excess of Nb ions over the number of niobium sites available in the stoichiometric lithium niobate structure. In a perfectly stoichiometric structure, each element occupies a well-defined position. However, in the case of non-stoichiometry or the presence of dopants, the total number of Nb ions may exceed the available Nb sites. This excess of Nb ions "creates" voids on other sites (such as Li or Mg) to compensate for the non-stoichiometry induced by x (lithium deficit) and y (dopant concentration, such as Mg).

For bivalent dopants such as magnesium (Mg), the situation becomes more complex. At low concentrations, bivalent dopants that replace Nb at Li sites can reduce the total number of vacancies by stabilizing the crystal lattice.

Defect dynamics in lithium niobate are therefore not limited to simple void compensation, but also involve void creation, depending on dopant type and concentration. Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for modeling and optimizing the properties of lithium niobate in critical applications such as surface acoustic wave (SAW) devices.

Table 1- Indicates the lacunar models used for undoped and doped lithium niobate.

Dopant	Concentration	Model
Magnesium (Mg)	0 < [Mg] < 3 mol%	$\left[Li_{Li\ 1-5x-2y}Nb_{Li\ x}Mg_{Li\ y}\square_{Li\ 4x+y}\right][Nb_{Nb}][O_3]$ [27]
	[Mg] > 3.4%	$\left[Li_{Li\ 1-4x-4,25y}Mg_{Li\ 0,525y-0,5x}\square_{Li\ 4,5x+3,725y}\right]\left[Nb_{Nb\ 1+x+0,64y}\square_{Nb\ -(x+0,64y)}\right][O_3]$ [25]
Pure (Non-doped)		$\left[Li_{Li\ 1-5x}Nb_{Li\ \frac{19}{20}x}\square_{Li\ \frac{81}{20}x}\right]\left[Nb_{Nb\ 1+\frac{1}{20}x}\square_{Nb\ -\frac{1}{20}x}\right][O_3]$ [9]

Density functional theory (DFT) has become a prevalent tool for investigating how doping modifies the electronic structure and conductive behavior of lithium niobate (LiNbO₃), especially with magnesium (Mg) as a dopant. In the present work, simulations were carried out using the Quantum ESPRESSO package, which leverages pseudopotentials and a plane-wave basis set to model atomic-scale material characteristics. Supercell models, comprising between 80 and 270 atoms depending on the dopant concentration, were designed to account for both local structural changes and extended lattice disturbances induced by dopants. In these models, lithium (Li) sites were partially substituted with Mg atoms at doping levels ranging from 2% up to 33.3%. Structural optimization was executed by relaxing atomic positions until the residual Hellmann-Feynman forces fell below 0.01 eV/Å.

Electronic density of states (DOS) was computed using the generalized gradient approximation (GGA), employing the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional. For Brillouin zone integration, Monkhorst-Pack grids were utilized, with 3×3×3 and 4×4×4 k-point meshes applied to large (270 atoms) and small (80 atoms) supercells, respectively, ensuring accurate convergence of the computed energies and electronic states.

Prior theoretical studies have extensively explored LiNbO₃ crystals using DFT. For instance, Zhang et al. [30] investigated how different dopants influence both structural and electronic aspects of LiNbO₃, emphasizing the stabilizing influence of Mg and Zr⁴⁺ on the lattice and their effects on polarization behavior. Additionally, Schmidt et al. [31,32] focused on the role of defects such as polarons and excitons, shedding light on mechanisms of charge trapping and associated distortions in the crystal matrix.

Table 2 the chemical formula of congruent lithium niobate ($r=0.9372$) for different concentrations of MgO (y).

Mg%	X%	Model 1 and 2
0%	1,057	$[Li_{0.9471}][Nb_{1.0105}]□_{0.0422}O_3$
1%	0,72	$[Li_{0.9408}][Nb_{1.007}]Mg_{0.01}□_{0.03881}O_3$
2%	0,383	$[Li_{0.94082}][Nb_{1.00383}]Mg_{0.02}□_{0.03533}O_3$
3%	0,0465	$[Li_{0.93767}][Nb_{1.0047}]Mg_{0.03}□_{0.03186}O_3$
3.12%	0,00617	$[Li_{0.9371}][Nb_1]Mg_{0.0312}□_{0.0314}O_3$
6%	6,964	$[Li_{0.9281}][Nb_{0.9903}]Mg_{0.06}□_{0.0214}O_3$

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Electrical conductivity of pure lithium niobate

In this section, we determine the electrical conductivity (σ) of different samples (samples 1, 2 and 3) of undoped lithium niobate with molar ratios $r_1 = [Li]/[Nb] = 48.3/51.7$, $r_2 = 49.5/50.5$ and $r_3=1$ respectively (Table 3), which were experimentally treated by A. Weidenfelder and al. Using the lacunar model we proposed [9], we were able to match the theoretical and experimental electrical conductivity results by computer simulations, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure .3 Comparison of experimental [24] and theoretical electrical conductivities of undoped lithium niobate samples (1, 2 and 3) as a function of $1000/T$.

The evolution of the logarithm of the electrical conductivity for different samples (samples 1, 2 and 3) of pure lithium niobate as a function of the inverse of temperature is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that the conductivity decreases with increasing lithium concentration (Li₂O), as also shown in Table 3. This indicates that stoichiometric samples have a lower conductivity than non-stoichiometric samples with a molar ratio of $r=Li/Nb$ less than 1. In other words, compositions with less lithium, which have more vacancies have a lower activation energy (Table 2), also favour ionic conduction. Using the

proposed mixed vacancy model and the phase transition theory we have proposed, we obtain a correspondence between the theoretical and experimental evolution of conductivity as a function of the inverse of temperature. The mixed vacancy model therefore provides (Table 1) a better description of the structure of point defects in lithium niobate (LN).

Table 3 electronic conductivities (at 7000°C), activation energies and lithium concentration for various LN samples [24]

Sample	Li ₂ O(mol%)	E _A (ev)	σ at 700°C (10 ⁻⁴ Smm ⁻¹)
Sample 1	48.3	1.37	17.8
Sample 2	49.5	1.44	9.95
Sample 3	50	1.49	<7.23

3.2 Electrical Conductivity of Magnesium-Doped Lithium Niobate

The electrical conductivity of magnesium-doped lithium niobate (Mg-doped LN) behaves differently from that of pure lithium niobate. The presence of magnesium ions in the crystal structure affects both the concentration of charge carriers and the structure of defects [33,34]. As the magnesium doping level increases, additional cationic vacancies are introduced, affecting the ionic conductivity of the material. Experimental results indicate that the electrical conductivity varies significantly as a function of temperature and doping concentration. In this section, we examine the effect of doping on congruent lithium niobate (c-LN) by comparing our results, presented in Figure 4, with those obtained

experimentally by Nadège Meyer et al [25].

Figure 4 Logarithms of experimental (Exp) [25] and theoretical conductivity of undoped and doped c.LN with different percentages of MgO (1%, 3%, 4%, 5% and 6%) as a function of reverse temperature (1000/T). The curves were plotted using the equations given in Table 4.

Analysis of Figure 4 reveals significant trends in the electrical conductivity of magnesium oxide (MgO)-doped lithium niobate (LiNbO₃) samples as a function of dopant concentration. In general, conductivity decreases with increasing reverse temperature. At low MgO concentrations, conductivity increases progressively. We also observed good overall agreement between our theoretical results and the experimental data (Exp Mg0 and Exp Mg5) [25].

Conductivity increases with MgO content up to a critical threshold of around 3.4%. Above this concentration, conductivity begins to decrease. As shown in Figure 5 (c), this critical point corresponds to a structural transition in which niobium cations no longer occupy lithium sites in the LiNbO₃ crystal lattice, as shown in Figure 5 (d) [25].

This structural change is crucial: excess magnesium leads to a reduction in the active niobium content and favours the formation of structural defects and additional charge-trapping sites, thereby reducing the electrical conductivity of the material. The 3.4% threshold must therefore be carefully considered when designing doped materials, in order to optimise their electrical properties without introducing damaging structural instabilities.

Tableau 4 Analytical expression of logarithmic conductivity at 700°C as a function of μ ($\mu = 103/T$) for different percentages of Mg in lithium niobate (sample 1).

Concentration of Mg(mol%)	$\alpha = A + B\mu$
0%(Mg0)	$\alpha = 14.3654 - 12.5954\mu$
1%(Mg1)	$\alpha = 14.3654 - 12.4922\mu$
3%(Mg3)	$\alpha = 14.3654 - 12.2855\mu$
4%(Mg4)	$\alpha = 14.3654 - 12.5277\mu$
5%(Mg5)	$\alpha = 14.3654 - 12.9604\mu$
6%(Mg6)	$\alpha = 14.3654 - 13.4087\mu$

We have also analyzed the impact of doping congruent lithium niobate with magnesium on conductivity at constant temperatures using equation 13. The results of this analysis are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. (c); Variation in LN ionic conductivity as a function of Mg content at different temperatures and , (d); Nb_{Li} concentrations (x) in each impurity-doped LN (sample 1) as a function of impurity concentration (y).

Figure 5(c) illustrates the variation of the logarithm of conductivity ln(σ) as a function of magnesium concentration in non-stoichiometric lithium niobate (sample 1) at different temperatures. It is clearly observed that the conductivity of magnesium-doped lithium niobate increases with temperature. Furthermore, at constant temperature, conductivity exhibits an upward trend with increasing magnesium concentration (y) up to approximately 3.4%, beyond which it begins to decrease linearly. This initial increase in conductivity can be attributed to both the reduction of structural defects induced by the incorporation of magnesium ions (Nb_{Li}), as shown in Figure 5(d), and the narrowing of the band gap energy (E_g), as shown in Figure 7. However, beyond this critical threshold, the band gap

E_g begins to widen, and the substitution mechanism leads to a reduction in lithium and niobium concentrations in the lithium niobate structure, thereby increasing the proportion of structural defects (Table 2). This accumulation of defects disrupts charge carrier transport, resulting in a decline in conductivity even as the magnesium concentration continues to increase.

Therefore, the electrical conductivity of magnesium-doped lithium niobate is influenced by both temperature and magnesium concentration. The effect of doping on conductivity is highly dependent on these parameters, highlighting the importance of precise control over doping concentration and thermal conditions to optimize the material's electrical properties.

Table 5- The composition of the non-stoichiometric x and the band gap ΔE_g for different samples of lithium niobate at $t=25^\circ\text{C}$.

Samples	Band gap ΔE_g (eV) (GGA-PBE result)					
	This work	Other work	Ref	Experimental Ref	result	
LN CG	3.58	3.61				
		[35]				
		3.50			3.72	[38]
		[36]				
LN MG1 : (Mg 2%)	3.32	3.48				
		[37]			3.65 for LN: (Mg 0.35%)	[38]
		--		3.63 for LN: (Mg 0.63%)	[38]	
LN MG2 : (Mg 4 %)	3.59	--		3.87 for LN: (Mg 5%)	[39]	
LN MG3 : (Mg 16 %)	3.63	--		3.90 for LN: (Mg 7%)	[39]	

3.3 Effect of point defects on the conductivity of undoped and MgO-doped LN

Measurements of σ -conductivity and analyses of the defect structure of MgO-doped LN show that σ depends on the concentration of the non-stoichiometric x -composition. To confirm this dependence in the case of LN doped with other impurities, σ was determined for c-LN doped with magnesium Mg,

maintaining a congruent Li/Nb ratio.

Figure 6. Electrical conductivity of Mg-doped LN (sample 1) as a function of composition x .

Figure 6 shows the variation in electrical conductivity (σ) as a function of structural defect concentration (x) for three magnesium-doped lithium niobate samples, S_1 , S_2 and S_3 . A general trend emerges: as the concentration of structural defects (x) increases, the electrical conductivity (σ) decreases. This trend is consistent with what is observed in many materials where the presence of defects in the crystalline structure can disrupt the mobility of charge carriers, leading to a decrease in electrical conductivity. It is important to note that sample 1 has a significantly higher electrical conductivity than samples 2 and 3. The electrical conductivity of magnesium-doped lithium niobate therefore decreases with increasing concentration of structural defects. Furthermore, the chemical composition, in particular the lithium concentration, has a significant impact on electrical conductivity, which is higher in the sample with the lower lithium concentration.

3.4 Impact of LN MgO doping on the density of electronic states (DOS) and Band structure

The density of states (DOS) and band structure of doped and undoped lithium niobate (LiNbO_3) have been determined using density functional theory (DFT) calculations. Figure 7 shows the DOS for congruent lithium niobate (c.LN) (a), lithium niobate doped with 2% magnesium (LNMg, Mg 2%) (b). Figure 10 shows the band structure of c.LN (d) and LNMg doped with 2% magnesium (e).

Figure 7 Densité partielle d'états (DOS) pour (a) : c.LN congru et (b) : (LNMg).

The band gap energy for c.LN is $E_g=3.58\text{eV}$ (see Table 5). For magnesium-doped lithium niobate, we observed that at low MgO concentrations (below the critical threshold of (3.4 mol%), the bandgap energy is lower than that of c.LN. Consequently, the conductivity of c.LN is lower than that of magnesium-doped lithium niobate at low concentrations. However, at higher MgO concentrations, the band gap E_g increases, leading to a decrease in conductivity (σ) as the MgO concentration increases, in agreement with the results in Figure 5.

Figure 8 Structures de bandes de (d) : c.LN et (e) : LNMg avec 2% de Mg.

Figure 9. Bandgap energy (E_g) and logarithmic electrical conductivity (σ) for: (g) LN doped with MgO.

The results presented in Figures 9 and 5 clearly illustrate the significant influence of selective doping on the electrical conductivity of congruent lithium niobate (LN). Our findings show that the conductivity of LN increases with the addition of magnesium oxide (MgO), reaching a peak at approximately 3.4% doping. Beyond this point, however, the conductivity begins to decline. This critical threshold appears to mark a structural transition, where the beneficial impact of magnesium incorporation is offset by the formation of defect-related complexes.

This trend is closely tied to variations in the material's bandgap energy (E_g). When the MgO concentration is below 3.4%, the bandgap gradually narrows as the doping level rises. This reduction in E_g lowers the energy needed for charge carriers to become excited, thereby facilitating conduction. At the same time, the number of Nb antisite defects (Nb_{Li}) decreases, which further improves charge mobility and contributes to enhanced conductivity.

On the other hand, when the MgO content exceeds 3.4%, the bandgap begins to widen again. This shift is attributed to the accumulation of structural imperfections that inhibit carrier movement, ultimately leading to reduced conductivity.

These results are consistent with previously published experimental measurements of electrical resistance in polycrystalline LN doped with Mg and Zn. In particular, Mg-doped LN demonstrates a lower resistance value (7.61 G Ω) compared to both undoped LN (8.35 G Ω) and Zn-doped LN (9.80 G Ω) [34]. This decline in resistance aligns well with our observations of improved conductivity at moderate magnesium levels, confirming that Mg serves as an effective dopant—provided its

concentration remains below a certain threshold. Beyond that point, its presence becomes counterproductive.

Overall, these findings underscore the importance of optimizing dopant concentration to enhance the electrical performance of LN, particularly in applications like surface acoustic wave (SAW) devices and optical modulators, where precise control over electronic properties is essential.

4. Conclusion

This study highlights the critical impact of targeted doping concentrations on the electronic properties of lithium niobate (LN). In particular, our investigation focuses on an optimal magnesium doping level of 3.4%, identified as a critical threshold beyond which the material's electrical performance significantly changes. At this concentration, electrical conductivity is maximized due to a reduction in non-stoichiometric defects (Nb_{Li}) and a narrowing of the bandgap (E_g), which enhances charge carrier transport.

However, exceeding this threshold leads to increased structural defects and a widening of the bandgap, which in turn reduces electron mobility and electrical conductivity. These findings, derived from a combined approach using phase transition theory and density functional theory (DFT) simulations, validate vacancy models for both pure and doped LN.

This work provides a valuable framework for optimizing LN-based materials in advanced applications, particularly in optoelectronics, nonlinear optics, and surface acoustic wave (SAW) resonators, where precise doping control is a key factor in device performance.

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